

Study of Histopathological Patterns of Endometrium in Abnormal Uterine Bleeding

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Abstract

Background: Abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) is a common gynecological complaint which has significant morbidity as well as plays an important role in affecting patients' personal and social life. The aim of this study was to analyze histo-morphological patterns of endometrium in patients with complain of AUB and also in determining the incidence of AUB in various age groups.

Material and Methods: This is a prospective study conducted with 156 endometrial specimens with clinical diagnosis of AUB in the department of pathology, ACPM Medical College, Dhule, Maharashtra. Analysis was done in the form of percentages and proportions and represented on tables wherever necessary.

Result: Majority of patients were from 46-55 years age group. Most common complaint was menorrhagia which accounted for 47%. Moreover commonest pathology observed in the study was endometrial hyperplasia.

Conclusion: On evaluation from the samples collected, incidence of AUB was seen in different age groups. In patients with no organic pathology, normal physiological patterns with proliferative, secretory, and menstrual changes were observed. Histopathological evaluation of endometrial samples was done to rule out malignancy and pre-neoplasia.

Keywords: Abnormal uterine bleeding, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, Dilation and curettage (D&C), endometrium.

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Introduction

Abnormal Uterine Bleeding (AUB) is defined as any type of bleeding that does not fall within the normal ranges for frequency, amount, duration, or cyclicity. [1] AUB is presented as menorrhagia, inter-menstrual bleeding, polymenorrhoea and metrorrhagia. Dilatation and Curettage (D & C) is the mainstay of endometrial

sampling. D and C also allows for a fractional curettage with separate sampling of both the endocervical and endometrial tissues. Hysteroscopy has replaced blind curettage as the uterine cavity can be observed and the area in question can be curetted. Trans-vaginal/trans-abdominal ultrasonography is another useful adjunctive technique for the examination

of the endometrium in the evaluation of AUB. [1-3] The underlying diseases can be detected well by histological variations of endometrium taking into account the age of the woman, phase of her menstrual cycle, and the use of any exogenous hormones. Hyperplasia is found in almost 16% and endometrial carcinoma in around 10% of postmenopausal patients undergoing biopsy. [2] Patients with history of obesity, anovulation, diabetes, hypertension and exogenous estrogen use are at a higher risk for hyperplasia and adeno-carcinoma. [2] Early evaluation in peri-menopausal and post-menopausal women are essential to confirm the exact nature of the lesion and to rule out malignancy if any.

Materials and Methods

Patients who presented in this hospital with a history of AUB from April 2021 to April 2022 and had underwent D&C or hysterectomy was included in this study. Patients with gestational cause, hemostatic disorders, vaginal pathology and

leiomyoma were excluded. Relevant clinical history regarding age, pattern and duration of abnormal bleeding, obstetric history, menstrual history, use of exogenous hormones, physical as well as gynecological examination findings, lab investigation results and hysteroscopic findings were obtained from casefiles from Medical Records Department. All the specimens (3-4µ thick sections) were fixed in 10% formalin, processed and embedded in paraffin. Sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin stain. A total of 156 cases were analyzed. Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and managed in SPSS version [16]. Analysis was done in the form of percentages and proportions and represented as tables.

Results

A total of 156 endometrial specimens submitted with a clinical diagnosis of AUB. Patients age ranged between 23 to 78 years and majority were seen in the age group of 46-55 years, followed by 36-45 years as described in [Table 1].

Table 1: Distribution of patients with abnormal uterine bleeding in various age groups.

Age (in years)	No. of patients	Percentage
<35	13	8.33
35-45	62	39.75
46-55	67	42.95
>55	14	8.97
Total	156	100.0

The commonest complaint was menorrhagia in 73 patients (47%). Seventy five (48.4%) of them were in the low parity group (para 1-2) followed by para 3-4 (32.4%). The commonest pathology observed in the study was endometrial hyperplasia in 39(25%) patients. Secretory

endometrium was the next commonly observed pattern seen in 26(16.7%) patients, followed by proliferative and disordered proliferative endometrium in 19(12.2%) patients each. Endometrial carcinoma was seen in 7 (4.5%) cases as described in [Table 2].

Table 2 : Distribution of endometrial patterns in abdominal uterine bleeding patients.

Endometrial pattern	No of patients	Percentage
Proliferative phase endometrium	19	12.2
Secretory phase endometrium	26	16.7
Mixed pattern		3.84
Pill endometrium	12	7.7

Disordered proliferative endometrium	19	12.2
Luteal phase defect	4	2.6
Menstrual endometrium	2	1.28
Atrophic endometrium	8	5.12
Endometritis	1	0.64
Endometrial polyps	8	5.12
Endometrial hyperplasia	39	25
Endometrial carcinoma	7	4.5
Endometrial Stromal Sarcoma	1	0.64
Other carcinomas	2	1.28
Inadequate	2	1.28
Total	156	100.0

Table 3 : Correlation of ultrasonography, hysteroscopy and hypersensitivity pneumonitis in diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia.

	Hysteroscopy hyperplasia	Hyperplasia	ET (mm)
Hysteroscopy hyperplasia	1.000	Poor correlation (0.025)	Fair correlation (0.350)
Hyperplasia	0.025	1.000	Fair correlation (0.350)
ET (mm)	0.350	0.205	1.000

Discussion

AUB accounts for around 25% of gynecological operations and 20% of outpatient visits. [3] In the present study, we have studied the histopathology of endometrium to identify endometrial causes and also observe the incidence of various pathologies in different age groups and also their relation to parity.

In this study, the maximum incidence of AUB was seen in 46-55 years age group (67 patients), followed by 36-45 years age group (62 patients). Our study and other studies have found a maximum incidence of AUB in the perimenopausal age group.[4-10] As women approach menopause, cycles shortens and often become intermittently anovulatory due to decline in the number of ovarian follicles and fluctuations in the estradiol level leading to various patterns of abnormal bleeding. [2] Our study and other studies have found menorrhagia as the commonest complaint. [4,5,7,8] Endometrial hyperplasia was the most common histological pattern observed in our study and was seen in 39 cases (25%). Few studies have reported a similar incidence

with 24.7% and 26%, respectively. [5,13] However, many other studies have observed a lower incidence for about 12.6%, 15%, and 4.33%. [8,14,15] In the present study, the maximum incidence of hyperplasia was noted in the age group of 46-55 and was seen in 22 of 39 patients (56.4%). This was consistent with the findings in other studies. [5,13,14,16,17] In this study, there was a fair correlation between findings of increased endometrial thickness by ultrasonography and histopathological diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia, but there was a poor correlation between hysteroscopic and histopathological diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia [Table 3] which was calculated by Spearman Correlation. In this study, predominant number of patients in the age group of 36-45 years showed normal physiological changes like proliferative and secretory phase patterns. Secretory endometrium was the second most common pattern observed in this study and was seen in 26 patients (16.7%). Similar incidence of secretory pattern (16.6%) was noted in another study.⁷The bleeding in secretory phase is due to

ovulatory dysfunctional uterine bleeding and characterized by regular episodes of heavy menstrual blood loss. The main defect is in the control of processes regulating the volume of blood lost during the menstrual breakdown of endometrium. [20] This pattern was commonly observed in the late reproductive and perimenopausal women in our study and other studies and may be due to the hormonal imbalance in this group leading to intermittent anovulatory cycles. Atrophic endometrium is the commonest cause of bleeding in post-menopausal stage. [12] Thin walled veins, superficial to the expanding cystic glands, makes the vessels vulnerable to injury and often lead to massive uterine bleeding. 16 Atrophic endometrium was seen in 5.13% of the patients in this study and they presented as post-menopausal bleeding. A similar incidence was reported in other studies with incidences of 4.34% and 7%, respectively. [12,25] In this study, pill endometrium was seen in 12 cases (7.69%). Other studies shows a lower incidence. [5,13,24] In this pattern, the endometrium shows a combination of inactive glands, abortive secretions, thin blood vessels, decidual reaction. [26] This pattern was seen in the peri-menopausal age group. This was probably due to increased number of patients in this age group resorting to early medical consultation for bleeding. Other benign patterns includes endometrial polyps (5.12%), irregular shedding (3.84%), luteal phase defects (2.56%), menstrual pattern (1.28%) and endometritis (0.64%). The most common presentation in patients of serous carcinoma and clear cell carcinoma was post-menopausal bleeding and incidence of endometrial carcinoma 21.73% in the postmenopausal group. This was similar to that reported by Baral R with an incidence of 21%. [16] Primary cancer of cervix extending to the endometrium was observed in two cases (1.28%) and they presented with post-menopausal bleeding. This was consistent with the findings of

Ara S who reported an incidence of 1.24%. [25] Patient with low-grade Endometrial Stromal Sarcomas (ESS) was a 50-years old and presented with menorrhagia and mass in the pelvis. [27] In a previously reported study of 14 cases of low grade ESS, the most common presentation was vaginal bleed (86%), followed by pelvic mass (7%) and pelvic pain (7%). [28,29]

Conclusion

Endometrial lesions vary according to the age of the patient. Endometrial sampling by dilatation and curettage (D&C) is an effective and reliable diagnostic test. Clinical information regarding age, parity, menstrual history and imaging studies are important pre-requisites in the interpretation of endometrial samples. Dilatation and curettage (D&C) reveals endometrial patterns in various forms of AUB and also helps to exclude the presence of any organic pathology. Thus, histo-pathological evaluation of endometrium is especially indicated in women above the age of 35 years to rule out pre-neoplastic lesions and malignancies if any.

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